

Synthesis of Furano Compounds (XXXVI) Cyclodehydration of ω -Aryloxyacetophenones

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A number of 2-arylcoumarones have been synthesised by cyclodehydration of the corresponding ω -aryloxyacetophenones in presence of polyphosphoric acid at 135–40°. The migration of the aryl nucleus from position 3 to 2 during the cyclodehydration has been studied and unambiguous syntheses of the above coumarones are reported.

Migration of a phenyl group from position 3 (II) to position 2 (III) has been reported in the cyclodehydration of a general system (I) where $x = O, S$ or NH .

Mechanism of this type of migration in the cyclodehydration of phenacylphenyl sulphide (1, $x = S$) has been discussed by Rao and Tilak¹, while Davies *et al.*² have reported that cyclodehydration of ω -phenoxyacetophenone (IV; where $x = O$ in I) with polyphosphoric acid at 132° involved the initial formation of 3-phenylcoumarone (V). Because 2-phenylcoumarone (VI) is more conjugated as compared to 3-phenyl isomer (V), conjugation serves as driving force for the rearrangement of the phenyl group from position 3 to position 2, which is apparently an acid-catalysed reaction as the 3-phenylcoumarone does not isomerise to the 2-phenylcoumarone when heated alone at 132°. Probably a proton attacks on position 3 in (V) resulting in the formation of an intermediate ion (Va) which rearranges to give

1. D. S. Rao and B. D. Tilak, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, **18B**, 77.
2. W. Davies and S. Middleton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3544.

another carbonium ion (Vb). Alternatively (V) may give rise to the intermediate synartetic ion (Vc). Both (Vb) and (Vc) then result in 2-phenylcoumarone by the elimination of a proton.

Tilak and co-workers³ worked in the naphthylthionaphthene series and have reported that the cyclodehydration of α -naphthacylphenyl sulphide (VII) with polyphosphoric acid gave a mixture of 2- β -naphthylthionaphthene (VIII) and 3- α -naphthylthionaphthene (IX).

The formation of 2- β -isomer (VIII) was surprising as it involved migration as well as shifting in the position of attachment in the aryl nucleus. This observation led us to undertake similar studies on cyclodehydration in coumarone series.

To study this type of migration in ω -phenoxyacetylnaphthalenes, 2-bromoacetylnaphthalene was condensed with phenol and resulting phenoxy compound (X), when cyclodehydrated with polyphosphoric acid at 135–40°, gave good yields of 2-(2'-naphthyl) coumarone (XI) which proved to be identical with an unambiguous preparation of this compound from the keto-nitrile (XII)⁴.

Next, ω -phenoxy-1-acetylnaphthalene (XIII) was prepared from 1-bromoacetylnaphthalene, which in turn was obtained by bromination of a commercial sample of 1-acetylnaphthalene. Cyclodehydration of (XIII) as before, gave a mixture of 2-(2'-naphthyl)

3. T. Srinivas Murthi and B. D. Tilak, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19B**, 395.

4. J. N. Chatterjea and S. K. Roy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 98.

coumarone (XV) and 2-(1'-naphthyl) coumarone (XIV), the former being obtained in a small quantity. This supported the observation of Tilak *et al.* in the thionaphthene series, but when a pure ω -phenoxy-1-acetylnaphthalene was prepared from rigorously purified 1-acetylnaphthalene or 1-naphthoic acid and cyclodehydrated, only 2-(1'-naphthyl) coumarone (XIV) was obtained. This proves that the formation of 2-(2'-naphthyl) coumarone (XV) and possibly that of 2-(2'-naphthyl) thionaphthene (VIII) in case of Tilak *et al.* is not a case of isomerisation in position within the naphthalene nucleus. In both the cases the 2-(2'-naphthyl) isomer arises from the 2-acetylnaphthalene which invariably accompanies the commercial 1-acetylnaphthalene as impurity.

The cyclodehydration of ω -phenoxy-3-methoxy-acetophenone afforded 2-(3'-methoxyphenyl) coumarone (XVII), none of the isomeric product 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl) coumarone (XVIII) was detected in the rearrangement product. Authentic specimens of (XVII) and (XVIII) were secured by independent syntheses (*vide experimental*).

EXPERIMENTAL

ω -Phenoxy-2-acetylnaphthalene (X): A mixture of 2-bromo-acetylnaphthalene (10.5 g.) and freshly distilled phenol (4 g.) was dissolved in dry acetone (70 ml.). To this solution anhydrous potassium carbonate (25.0 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed gently on water bath for 6 hrs., with usual precautions to exclude moisture. The phenoxy compound was obtained as an oil which soon solidified (7.0 g.), m.p. 110–11°. It crystallised from ethanol in prisms, m.p. 115–16° (Lit.⁵; m.p. 82–4°). (Found: C, 82.20; H, 5.60. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$: C, 82.45; H, 5.34%).

2-(2'-Naphthyl) coumarone: The phenoxy compound (X; 2 g.) was added to polyphosphoric acid (20.0 g.) from phosphoric anhydride (11.0 g.) and phosphoric acid (5.5 ml.). The mixture was heated with constant stirring for 2 hrs. at 140°, under dry conditions and then cooled, decomposed with ice water, when 2-(2'-naphthyl) coumarone was separated. The compound crystallised from ethanol in colourless plates, m.p. 161°. (Found: C, 88.30; H, 5.20. $C_{18}H_{12}O$ requires: C, 88.53; H, 4.92%).

Condensation of 2-methoxybenzylcyanide with ethyl 2-naphthalene carboxylate: Ethyl 2-naphthalene carboxylate (5.0 g.; 0.025 moles) and 2-methoxybenzylcyanide (4.41 g.; 0.03 moles) were taken with a suspension of sodium hydride (1.44 g, 0.03 moles) in dry benzene (40 ml.) and the contents refluxed overnight. On working up as usual, keto-nitrile (XII) was obtained and crystallised from ethanol in white cubes (3.0 g.), m.p. 130–1°. (Found: C, 80.00; H, 5.20. $C_{20}H_{15}O_2N$ requires: C, 79.73; H, 4.98%).

5. J. N. Chatterjea and S. K. Roy, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 144.

2-(2'-Naphthyl) coumarone : The above keto-nitrile (XII; 1.0 g.), was mixed with hydrobromic acid (10 ml.; 48%) and acetic acid (10 ml.) and the mixture refluxed on sand bath for 3 hrs. The solution was cooled and poured on to crushed ice, when a brown solid was precipitated, which crystallised from ethanol in colourless plates, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the specimen prepared by the first method 160°.

ω-Phenoxy-1-acetylnaphthalene (XIII) : Phenol (10.0 g.) and 1-bromoacetylnaphthalene (25.0 g.) (prepared by bromination of 1-acetylnaphthalene and purified by way of the picrate) were dissolved in dry acetone (100 ml.). Anhydrous potassium carbonate (54.0 g.) was then added to the mixture which was then gently refluxed on water bath for 8 hrs., with exclusion of moisture. On working up as usual, *ω*-phenoxy-1-acetylnaphthalene was obtained as a viscous oil which distilled at 190–5°/1.0 mm. as faintly yellow oil (15.0 g.). (Found : C, 82.20; H, 5.60. C₁₈H₁₄O₂ requires : C, 82.45; H, 5.34%).

The same compound was obtained from 1-chloroacetylnaphthalene which was prepared from pure 1-diazoacetylnaphthalene. It gave an orange yellow 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone from acetic acid, m.p. 200°. (Found : N, 12.60; C₂₄H₁₈O₅N₄ requires : N, 12.60%).

2-(1'-Naphthyl) coumarone : Polyphosphoric acid from phosphoric anhydride (5.5 g.) and phosphoric acid (2.8 ml.) was stirred at 140° with above phenoxy compound (XIII; 1.0 g.) for 10 hrs. The mixture was then cooled, decomposed with crushed ice and the resulting oil extracted with ether. The ether solution was dried (MgSO₄) and ether removed. A brown oil was obtained which yielded a red 2,4,6-trinitrofluorenone derivative from ethanol, m.p. 127–8°. (Found : N, 7.6. C₃₁H₁₇O₈N₃ requires : N, 7.5%).

Alternative synthesis : Ethyl 1-naphthoate (3.45 g.) and 2-methoxybenzyl cyanide (3.04 g.) were taken with a suspension of sodium hydride (1.0 g.) in dry benzene (40 ml.) and the mixture refluxed overnight. On working up as usual, the ketonitrile *α*-(1'-naphthoyl)-2-methoxybenzyl cyanide was obtained which crystallised from ethanol in colourless prisms, m.p. 122–3°. (Found : C, 79.50; H, 5.20. C₂₀H₁₅O₂N requires : C, 79.73; H, 4.98%).

2-(1'-Naphthyl) coumarone : The foregoing keto-nitrile (1.0 g.) was mixed with hydrobromic acid (10 ml.; 48%) and acetic acid (10 ml.). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. On working up, an oil was obtained which gave a red, 2,4,6-trinitrofluorenone derivative, identical with the T.N.F. derivative obtained by the first method (m.p. and mixed m.p. 127–8°).

ω-Phenoxy-3-methoxyacetophenone (XVI) : Freshly distilled phenol (0.94 g.) and *m*-methoxyphenacylbromide (2.29 g.) were dissolved in dry acetone (25 ml.). Anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.0 g.) was added and the mixture gently refluxed on water bath for 8 hrs. under dry conditions and worked up as before, to give *ω*-phenoxy-3-methoxyacetophenone (2.0 g.) as an oil which solidified and crystallised from ethanol in yellowish prisms, m.p. 52°. (Found : C, 74.00; H, 6.10. C₁₅H₁₄O₃ requires : C, 74.39; H, 5.78%).

2-(3'-Methoxyphenyl) coumarone : Polyphosphoric acid (20.0 g.) prepared by dissolving phosphoric anhydride (11.0 g.) in phosphoric acid (5.5 ml.) was preheated in an oil bath. The above phenoxy compound (XVI; 2.0 g.) was then added to it and heated at this

temperature with constant stirring for further 2 hrs. The mixture was then cooled and decomposed with iced water. An oil was obtained which was extracted with ether, and the ether solution dried (MgSO_4). On removing ether, the coumarone was obtained as an oil. 2,4,6-Trinitrofluorenone complex crystallised in lemon yellow needles from ethanol, m.p. 161–2°. (Found : C, 62.4; H, 3.30; N, 8.0. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_9\text{N}_3$ requires : C, 62.33; H, 3.15; N, 7.7%.)

α -(3'-Methoxybenzoyl)-2-methoxybenzyl cyanide : Ethyl 3-methoxybenzoate (1.64 g.; 0.01 mole) and 2-methoxybenzyl cyanide (1.76 g.; 0.012 mole) were added to a suspension of sodium hydride (0.58 g.; 0.012 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml.). The mixture was refluxed overnight, cooled and a few drops of ethanol were added to decompose the excess of the hydride. After decomposing carefully with water, the aqueous layer was acidified and extracted with ether, dried (MgSO_4) and the solvent evaporated off. The keto-nitrile (1.2 g.) crystallised from ethanol in colourless prisms, m.p. 70°. (Found : C, 72.40; H, 5.60. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires : C, 72.59; H, 5.33%.)

2-(3'-Hydroxyphenyl) coumarone : To a solution of the foregoing keto-nitrile (2.0 g.) in acetic acid (20 ml.), hydrobromic acid (20 ml.; 48%) was added and the mixture gently refluxed over sand bath for 3 hrs., cooled and poured onto crushed ice, when a gummy solid was obtained. 2-(3'-Hydroxyphenyl) coumarone crystallised from dilute acetic acid in greyish prisms, m.p. 131–2°. (Found : C, 79.80; H, 5.00. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 80.00; H, 4.76%.)

2-(3'-Methoxyphenyl) coumarone : The foregoing hydroxy compound (1.05 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml.; 10%) and dimethyl sulphate (2.5 ml.) was added portionwise. The oil obtained, was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer dried (MgSO_4). On removing the solvent, an oil was obtained which solidified on distillation. 2-(3'-Methoxyphenyl) coumarone was crystallised from ethanol in prisms, m.p. 51°. (Found : C, 80.10; H, 5.60. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 80.37; H, 5.35%.)

It gave a 2,4,6-trinitrofluorenone complex, m.p. 162–3°, identical with the specimen of T.N.F. complex obtained earlier (mixed m.p. 162–3°).

Condensation of 2-methoxybenzylcyanide with ethyl 4-methoxybenzoate : Ethyl 4-methoxybenzoate (1.8 g.; 0.01 mole) and 2-methoxybenzyl cyanide (1.76 g.; 0.012 mole) were taken with a suspension of sodium hydride (0.58 g.) in benzene (25 ml.) and the mixture refluxed overnight. On working up as usual, the keto-nitrile *α -(4'-methoxybenzyl)-2-methoxybenzyl cyanide* solidified and crystallised from ethanol in colourless prisms, m.p. 108°. (Found : C, 72.40; H, 5.60. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires : C, 72.59; H, 5.30%.)

2-(4'-Hydroxyphenyl) coumarone : The above keto-nitrile (2.0 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml.) was demethylated and cyclized by boiling with hydrobromic acid (20 ml.; 48%) for 3 hrs. The solution was then cooled and poured on to crushed ice yielding a solid 2-(4'-hydroxyphenyl) coumarone which crystallised from dilute acetic acid in greyish solid, m.p. 185–86°. (Found : C, 80.10; H, 5.00. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 80.00; H, 4.76%.)

2-(4'-Methoxyphenyl) coumarone (XVIII) : The foregoing hydroxycoumarone (1.0 g.) was taken in sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml.; 10%) and dimethyl sulphate (2 ml.) was

added dropwise with stirring. 2-(4'-Methoxyphenyl) coumarone, which precipitated, was collected and crystallised from ethanol in colourless prisms, m.p. 151° (lit.⁶, m.p. 152°). This coumarone was different from the 2-(3'-methoxyphenyl) coumarone (by direct comparison, mixed m.p.). (Found: C, 80.00; H, 5.50. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₂O₂: C, 80.35; H, 5.35%).

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6. M. M. Bokadia, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3308.